

GENDER AS A SOCIO-CULTURAL CONCEPT OF GENDER, ITS MANIFESTATION IN LANGUAGE AND SPEECH

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Abstract: In recent years, the linguistic component has become actively involved in the structure of the interdisciplinary concept of gender studies. Attention is focused on the socio-cultural conditionality of gender-role behavior, on the institutional nature of gender, where gender is viewed not as a natural phenomenon, but as a dynamically changing factor in the development of human society. This phenomenon lends itself to social modeling. If we analyze all kinds of sources on the study of gender as a social construct, then genderology, not least, refers to the analysis of the verbalized products of the linguistic consciousness of men and women in order to identify in it a manifestation of gender and its culturally marked specificity.

Theoretical and applied aspects of the problem of gender differences are considered: issues of the development of gender psychology in our country and abroad, the relevance of gender studies at the present stage of development of society. Gender differences are analyzed as a socio-cultural phenomenon closely related to the main strategies for the development of society.

Keywords: gender identity, gender stereotypes, psychological gender, gender ideals, gender role, social construct, socio-cultural phenomenon.

Аннотация: В последние годы лингвистический компонент занимает всё более значимое место в структуре междисциплинарной парадигмы гендерных исследований. Особое внимание уделяется социокультурной обусловленности гендерно-ролевого поведения, а также институциональной природе гендера, который рассматривается не как биологически заданное явление, а как динамически изменяющийся фактор развития человеческого общества. Данный феномен поддаётся социальному моделированию.

Анализ источников, посвящённых изучению гендера как социального конструкта, свидетельствует о том, что гендерология в значительной степени опирается на исследование вербализованных продуктов языкового сознания мужчин и женщин с целью выявления проявлений гендера и его культурно маркированной специфики.

В статье рассматриваются теоретические и прикладные аспекты проблемы гендерных различий, в том числе вопросы становления и развития гендерной психологии в отечественной и зарубежной научной традиции, а также актуальность гендерных исследований на современном этапе общественного развития. Гендерные различия анализируются как социокультурный феномен, тесно связанный с основными стратегиями развития общества.

Ключевые слова: Гендерная идентичность, гендерные стереотипы, психологический гендер, гендерные идеалы, гендерная роль, социальный конструкт, социокультурный феномен.

Annotatsiya: So'nggi yillarda lingvistik komponent gender tadqiqotlarining fanlararo paradigmasida tobora muhim o'rin egallamoqda. Tadqiqotlarda gender-rolli xulq-atvorning ijtimoiy-madaniy shartlanganligi hamda genderning institutsional tabiati alohida ta'kidlanadi. Gender biologik jihatdan belgilangan hodisa sifatida emas, balki inson jamiyati rivojida dinamik ravishda o'zgarib boruvchi omil sifatida talqin etiladi. Mazkur hodisa ijtimoiy modellashtirish imkoniyatiga ega. Genderni ijtimoiy konstrukt sifatida o'rganishga bag'ishlangan manbalarni tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatadiki, genderologiya erkaklar va ayollarning lingvistik ongida verballashgan mahsulotlarni tahlil qilishga murojaat qiladi. Bu esa genderning namoyon bo'lish shakllari va uning madaniy jihatdan belgilangan xususiyatlarini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Maqolada gender farqlari muammosining nazariy va amaliy jihatlari, jumladan, gender psixologiyasining mahalliy va xorijiy ilmiy an'analardagi rivojlanish masalalari hamda jamiyat taraqqiyotining hozirgi bosqichida gender tadqiqotlarining dolzarbligi yoritilgan. Gender farqlari jamiyat rivojining asosiy strategiyalari bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'lgan ijtimoiy-madaniy hodisa sifatida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Gender identifikatsiyasi, gender stereotiplari, psixologik gender, gender ideallari, gender roli, ijtimoiy konstrukt, ijtimoiy-madaniy hodisa.

It should be noted that in recent years in foreign and Kazakh psychology and sociology there has been a current increase in interest in social stereotypes in general and in sex-role stereotypes in particular. The study of a wide range of issues related to various aspects of gender role stereotypes is undoubtedly not only theoretical, but also of great practical importance.

The sociocultural concept of gender is realized within the framework of the masculinity / femininity dichotomy, which includes "a set of natural somatic, mental and behavioral features that distinguish a man from a woman recognized in a particular society and socially formalized in a given culture ... in the form of a complex of typified roles and statuses inherent only to this biological sex" [1].

There are a number of factors that shape a person's gender and, as a result, have an explanatory power of external manifestations of gender identity (in particular, language and speech).

Natural factors:

1. biological sex (morphophysiological differences, degree of adaptability, immunity);
2. ontogenetic mental signs (the degree of severity of aggressiveness and emotionality, the comparative speed and accuracy of psychomotor reactions, features of mental activity, differences in the time of onset of puberty, unrevealed or unknown differences).

Sociocultural factors:

1. gender ideals (ideals and anti-ideals in the process of socialization, attributed qualities, criteria for social assessment);
2. gender role (system of social statuses, system of social roles).

Behavior stands apart in this hierarchy as an integral characteristic (communication style, behavior style, lifestyle) [1].

Analyzing the mechanism of formation of gender differences, I.S. Kohn notes that in postnatal ontogenesis, the biological factors of sexual differentiation are supplemented by social ones. "This sexual socialization, the teaching of a child a sexual role," the author writes,

"is always derived from the norms and customs of the corresponding society and culture. This includes, first of all, the system of differentiation of sex roles (i.e., the sexual division of labor, specific gender-role prescriptions, the rights and obligations of men and women) and the system of stereotypes of masculinity / femininity associated with it, i.e. ideas about what men and women are or should be. Thus, according to I.S. Kohn, the psychosexual development of the child, determined by the genetic program, and the culturally provided gender socialization always operate and must be considered together, taking into account how they are refracted in the sexual self-consciousness of the individual.

The psychology of gender differentiation is currently not well understood. There are a number of alternative theories in this area [2], which can also be used in the combined study of behavioral responses:

1. Theory of identification (unconscious imitation of parents);
2. The theory of sex typing (sex typing), based on the theory of social learning and close to it the theory of modeling (encouragement and disapproval for incorrect masculine / feminine behavior);
3. The theory of self-categorization based on the cognitive genetic theory (founder L. Kohlberg). The child first learns a gender identity, and then tries to correlate his behavior with what, in his opinion, corresponds to such a definition;
4. New psychology of sex (social expectation of society, the influence of racial, class, ethnic variation of sex roles and the corresponding social expectation). For example, aggressive behavior is inherent in everyone equally from the moment of birth, but in the process of socialization in women it decreases, and in men it increases, because in women it is not approved in society, but in men it is vice versa.

Recent experiments in neurophysiology show that already in early childhood, the brain structures of boys and girls are very different. It has been proven that the brain develops mainly due to associative systems; in boys and girls of 3-4 years old, the brain has different associative systems: boys react to the semantic characteristics of a word, girls perceive only emotionally colored words [2].

Numerous experimental studies and longitudinal experiments prove that "... language as a social phenomenon, inevitably reflects social attitudes towards men and women. Social change and language change are mutually reinforcing" [3].

Each language necessarily reflects the social organization within society: both in ancient societies and in tribes living in isolation from modern civilization. Stratification variability, based on the simplest demographic parameters, is decisive.

The data of anthropological linguistics have shown that among the causes of language changes, an important place is occupied by those that are directly related to the division of society along gender lines. The most important of these are social organization, tabooing and exogamy, social morality, psychological characteristics [4].

Gender formation proceeds through several processes. Joan Ecker identifies several interacting gender agendas [5]:

1. construction of the division of labor, place of stay, physical space, permitted behavior, power, depending on gender;
2. creating symbols and images that explain, express, reinforce or oppose this division;

3. formation of gender components of individual identity or otherwise gender personality structures;

4. differences in interactions man / woman, woman / woman, man / man, manifested in speech, its interruption, in the order of dialogue, in the proposal of topics for dialogue, in non-verbal components of behavior.

Quite a lot of research on the characteristics of the speech of men and women has been carried out in recent years. Researchers have drawn some conclusions about these features. A woman, as it were, uses the core of the dictionary (an established layer of vocabulary). A man uses more neologisms, professionalisms and archaic forms of words, if he is not able to find a more common word or expression for them. A woman is more focused on her inner world, so she has more words in her speech related to emotions and feelings. In the speech of men, one can find more appeals to someone else's opinion, i.e. footnotes, quotes. Women in their assessments are always much more categorical than men. Men's associations are richer and more dispersed than women's. Women's ones are much more concentrated and have more matching associations [6].

Probably, such differences are caused by the fact that male and female at the ontological and epistemological levels exist as elements of cultural and symbolic series: male - rational, spiritual, cultural; feminine sensual, bodily, natural.

According to psychologists, gender identity is formed at the age of 5-7 years, and then it develops and is saturated with content through experiences and practices.

It should also be noted that E. Maccoby and K. Jacklin, after analyzing 1000 studies on the psychology of sex differences, came to the conclusion that, in essence, there are no fundamental sex differences in the psychological characteristics of men and women in many areas where these differences were previously recognized.

To what extent our studies correspond to this conclusion, we have to find out by analyzing some of the associative fields from the stimulus list.

Speaking about the formation of gender identity, L.V. Popova [7] highlights the main manifestations of gender (sex-role) socialization.

Having this or that influence on the self-actualization of the personality at different stages of the life path through the formation of the "I-image":

- gender identity in childhood;
- society's stereotypes regarding men and women;
- own expectations of men and women;
- representations and expectations of parents;
- mother and father as role models;
- experience gained in education;
- influence of peers.

It is these parameters that are of the greatest value in the analysis of male and female language and speech manifestations.

References:

1. Antineskul O.L. Gender as a parameter of text formation: diss.cand. philol. sciences. - Perm, 2000. - 222 p.
2. Bakusheva E.M. Sociolinguistic analysis of verbal behavior

3. men and women: diss. cand. philol. sciences. - M., 1995. - 193 p.
4. Goroshko E.I. An integrative model of an associative experiment. - M.; Kharkov: Ra-Karavella, 2001. - 553 p.
5. Klyuchko O.I. Man and woman. Problems of modern socialization. - Saransk, 2002. - 98 p.
6. Kon I.S. Human sexuality at the turn of the 21st century. // Questions
7. philosophy. - 2001. - №. 8. - 30-41 p.
8. Cheshire J. The relationship between language and sex in English // Linguistics for teachers. - Duluth, 1993. - 130 p.